

**ILMIY VA
INNOVATSION
TERAPIYA**

**SCIENTIFIC >>> >>>
AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

2025, № 2 (Май)

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

**SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

**ИЛМИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН
ТЕРАПИЯ**

**НАУЧНАЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ
ТЕРАПИЯ**

Научный журнал по научной и инновационной терапии
основано в 2022 году

Бухарским государственным медицинским институтом
имени Абу Али ибн Сино
выходит один раз в 2 месяца

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

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медицинский институт имени Абу Али ибн Сино*

ISSN
2181-418X

2025, № 2 (Май)

Адрес редакции:

Республика Узбекистан, 200100,
г. Бухара, ул. А. Гиждувани, 23.

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О журнале

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28.05.2022 г.

Подписано в печать 20.11.2023.

Формат 60×84 1/8

Усл. П.л. 41,39

Заказ 104

Тираж 50 экз.

Отпечатано в типографии Шарк

140151, г. Бухары,

ул. Амира Темура, 18

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FEATURES OF MENTAL CHANGES IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS WITH RESPIRATORY TUBERCULOSIS

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Currently, psychological support for patients is recognized as an integral element of the pulmonary tuberculosis treatment system. The purpose of our study was to study the personal characteristics of children and adolescents with respiratory tuberculosis and the relationship between parents in the families of patients. The study involved 92 patients with active respiratory tuberculosis and 84 healthy children and adolescents aged 8 to 17 years. They used a testing methodology aimed at self-assessment of patients. Thus, children and adolescents with respiratory disorders differ significantly from their healthy peers in their specific psychological characteristics. The approach, which involves the identification of pathogenetically important psychological mechanisms of the development of tuberculosis of the respiratory system, opens up opportunities for solving urgent problems related to maintaining the health of children and adolescents in modern society.

Key words: *tuberculosis of the respiratory system, children and adolescents, psychoemotional state, self-esteem.*

ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПСИХИЧЕСКИХ ИЗМЕНЕНИЙ У ДЕТЕЙ И ПОДРОСТКОВ С ТУБЕРКУЛЕЗОМ ОРГАНОВ ДЫХАНИЯ

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На сегодняшний день психологическая помощь пациентам является важной частью лечения туберкулеза органов дыхания. Наша работа была посвящена изучению индивидуальных черт характера у детей и подростков, страдающих туберкулезом дыхательных путей, а также анализу взаимосвязей

между родителями в семьях, где есть заболевшие дети туберкулезом. В исследовании участвовали 92 детей и подростка с активной формой туберкулеза органов дыхания и 84 детей и подростка в возрасте от 8 до 17 лет. Для оценки самовосприятия участников исследования была использована специальная методика тестирования. Результаты показали, что дети и подростки с туберкулезом значительно отличаются от здоровых ровесников по своим психологическим особенностям. Определение ключевых психологических факторов, влияющих на развитие туберкулеза органов дыхания, позволяет найти новые пути решения актуальных задач, связанных с сохранением здоровья подрастающего поколения.

Ключевые слова: туберкулез органов дыхания, дети и подростки, психоэмоциональное состояние, самооценка.

NAFAS A‘ZOLARI SILI BILAN KASALLANGAN BOLALAR VA
O‘SMIRLARDA RUHIY O‘ZGARISHLARNING XUSUSIYATLARI
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Hozirgi vaqtda bemorlarni psixologik qo‘llab-quvvatlash o‘pka silini davolash tizimining ajralmas elementi sifatida tan olingan. Tadqiqotimizning maqsadi nafas olish sili bilan og‘rigan bolalar va o‘smirlarning shaxsiy xususiyatlarini va bemorlarning oilalarida ota-onalar o‘rtasidagi munosabatlarning xususiyatlarini o‘rganish edi. Tadqiqotda 8 yoshdan 17 yoshgacha bo‘lgan faol nafas olish sil kasalligiga chalingan 92 nafar bemor va 84 nafar sog‘lom bolalar va o‘smirlar ishtirok etdi. Ularda bemorlarning o‘z-o‘zini baholashga qaratilgan test metodologiyasidan foydalanildi. Shunday qilib, nafas olish a‘zolari sili bilan og‘rigan bolalar va o‘smirlar sog‘lom tengdoshlaridan o‘ziga xos psixologik xususiyatlari bilan sezilarli darajada farq qiladi. Nafas olish tizimining sil kasalligi rivojlanishining patogenetik jihatdan muhim psixologik mexanizmlarini aniqlashni o‘z ichiga olgan yondashuv zamonaviy jamiyatda bolalar va o‘smirlarning salomatligini saqlash bilan bog‘liq dolzarb muammolarni hal qilish uchun imkoniyatlar ochadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: nafas olish sili, bolalar va o‘smirlar, psixo-emotsional holat, o‘z-o‘zini baholash.

Relevance. The problems of providing anti-tuberculosis care to children and adolescents are closely related to the epidemiological situation, which, despite stabilization in recent years, has become acute. Analysis of the causes of this situation showed that the fight against tuberculosis is not only a medical problem, but is

largely determined by the social conditions of society and the family. As a part of society, the family cannot remain unaffected by these problems. More than 60% of children with tuberculosis are from families facing various social problems (socially unadapted and families at medical and social risk). In this situation, a pressing scientific and practical problem of modern phthisiopediatrics is predicting the risk of developing tuberculosis infection in children and adolescents and adequately managing these risks [1-7,10]. Traditionally, great importance is attached to the epidemiological risk factor for the development of the disease in children and adolescents, especially family contact with a tuberculosis patient. Social risk factors that increase the likelihood of developing bacterial destruction processes, leading to a complex course of the disease, are also not overlooked [2,8,9]. Accordingly, in the innovative technologies currently being developed, the determination of the individual risk level of tuberculosis infection, as well as the volume of anti-tuberculosis care, is based on a complex of epidemiological, medical, and social factors [1,4,10]. Inclusion of targeted psychocorrective measures in the complex of preventive measures is necessary and methodologically justified.

Purpose. Study of the personal characteristics of children and adolescents with respiratory tuberculosis and the features of parental relationships in the families of patients.

Materials and methods: Comprehensive medical and psychological studies were conducted to determine the features of the psychosomatic state of children and adolescents with active respiratory tuberculosis. Data collection was carried out through testing, observing the principles of voluntariness and anonymity. The objectives of the test and the rules for filling out the questionnaire were explained to everyone, after which the test takers and parents independently filled out the questionnaire. 92 children and adolescents with active respiratory tuberculosis aged 8 to 17 years, who were treated in the children's department of the Samarkand Regional Center of Phthisiology and Pulmonology, were examined. The control group consisted of 84 healthy children and adolescents of the same age group. To determine the psycho-emotional state of the aforementioned contingent, the "HAM" (health status, activity and mood) test methodology, aimed at self-assessment of patients, was used.

Results and discussion. The results of the test to determine the psychosomatic state of children and adolescents with active respiratory tuberculosis showed the following (Table 1).

Table 1. Indicators of psycho-emotional state in children, adolescents, and healthy children with respiratory tuberculosis (based on the HAM test)

Scale	Main group n =92	Control group n = 84
Health status	3,45 ± 0,05	5,85 ± 0,06
Activity	3,61 ± 0,05	5,50 ± 0,05

Mood	$3,71 \pm 0,06$	$5,40 \pm 0,06$
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The following forms of tuberculosis were observed in children and adolescents with active respiratory tuberculosis (Fig. 1):

Figure 1. Tuberculosis forms observed in children and adolescents with respiratory tuberculosis

The personal characteristics of patients with this nosology were determined using the "self-assessment of personality" method (O.I. Motkov), which allowed us to study the general level of positive self-assessment of personality development, its individual factors and qualities, as well as the degree of its proportionality. The pseudo-high level of self-esteem ranged from 4,51-4,71 points to the maximum limit of 5,0 points, and the low level was in the range of 1,0-2,90. Both the groups of patients with respiratory tuberculosis and healthy individuals were identical in age composition. The average age in the main group was $14,3 \pm 0,7$ years, in the control group – $13,5 \pm 0,4$ years. The process of tuberculosis, diagnosed for the first time, was noted in $78,8 \pm 2,3\%$ of children in the main group, recurrence of the disease - in $2,4 \pm 4,8\%$. In the process of studying the personality profile and behavioral trends of children with respiratory tuberculosis and somatically healthy children aged 8-12 years, significant differences were revealed in some personality factors (R. Cattell questionnaire). In children with respiratory tuberculosis, personal qualities that contribute to the formation of neurotic disorders are more pronounced: lack of self-confidence, mood instability, anxiety, sadness (factor S: "emotional instability-emotional stability"). Almost a third of children in the main group have difficulty adapting to new conditions, feel weak, cannot cope with life difficulties, have low resistance to despair and difficult external situations. Comparative analysis of personality traits and behavioral trends in adolescent subgroups also revealed

significant differences compared to somatically healthy peers. Sick adolescents have a significantly higher score for factor I: "violence-sensitivity," which reflects their emotional sensitivity, variability under the influence of the environment, dependence on others, the need for affection and support (main group (MG) – 6,3; control group (CG) – 5,2; $p < 0,05$). As in the main group of children, personality traits, designated as "high normality" (G-factor), were significantly more common among sick adolescents: in MG - 71% of cases, in CG - 45%; $p < 0,05$. For them, the moral aspects of interpersonal relationships are also important, non-fulfillment or non-compliance is condemned, causes dissatisfaction, anger, and accusations from others. Adolescents with low standards, capable of conflict with parents and teachers, neglecting their duties, were identified in 19% of cases in the main group (CG - in 31% of cases; $p < 0,05$). This opposite combination of sensitivity and hypersocialization may indicate the existence of an internal contradiction between feeling and duty, which contributes to the emergence of internal conflict, problems of self-expression and self-regulation. Indirect confirmation of this is provided by data from the study of self-assessment of one's own personal qualities in a small group of somatically healthy and sick adolescents. In the main group, self-esteem significantly prevailed ($p < 0,05$): "sad" 55% (CG-16%) and "truthfulness" 33% (CG-18%). The presence of the following qualities was noted significantly less frequently: "unity," "independence," "selfishness" ($p < 0,05$).

Conclusion. Tuberculosis has the greatest negative impact on health. During prolonged treatment, fatigue increases in children and adolescents. Thus, children and adolescents with respiratory tuberculosis differ significantly from their healthy peers in their specific psychological characteristics: emotional instability, dependence on others, low emotional adaptability to situations of self-expression and self-evaluation, subjectively suspicious attitude towards others, alexithymic radical personality and normality. The identified features cause difficulties in interpersonal interaction with others and contribute to the emergence of long-term neuropsychological tension. Psychocorrective measures should be included in the tuberculosis treatment system for children and adolescents, the purpose of which is to change the specific psychological characteristics of patients. It is also necessary to conduct consultations with the parents and close relatives of patients aimed at creating more favorable conditions for the child's personal development. The approach, including the identification of pathogenetically significant psychological mechanisms of the development of respiratory tuberculosis, opens up opportunities for solving urgent problems related to the preservation of the somatic health of children and adolescents in modern society.

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